

Toward an in-depth fire hazard and resistance diagnosis of flame retarded liquid electrolytes for safer lithium-ion batteries

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Abstract

Growing reports of fire incidents originating from lithium-ion batteries have led to a quest for safer lithium-ion batteries. Although the commercial success of the lithium-ion batteries owes a great debt to the liquid electrolyte as much as the electrodes, the liquid electrolyte is considered the most flammable component of the battery. Flame retardant additives offer a promising solution to alleviate electrolyte flammability since they are added in minute quantities. However, the fire resistance and hazard diagnosis of the flame retardant containing liquid electrolyte remains a challenge due to the lack of reliable characterization technology. Herein, a stainless steel sample holder is custom-designed and integrated into the cone calorimeter, enabling a precise and reliable technique for diagnosing the fire resistance efficiency and hazards of flame retarded liquid electrolytes. This integration allows for real-time analysis of key fire behavior parameters of the flame retarded electrolytes such as time to ignition, heat release rate, fire growth rate index, smoke toxicity index, carbon monoxide, and smoke produced. Most of the fire test results show high reproducibility with less than 10% error. This study indicates that the modified cone calorimetry is a promising technology for diagnosing flame retarded liquid electrolyte fire resistance and hazard.

1. Introduction

A recent surge in lithium-ion battery-induced fires and explosions from portable electronics and electric vehicles has increased concerns about the safety of lithium-ion batteries, especially in electric vehicles that are often powered by thousands of lithium-ion battery cells^[1-3]. The lithium-ion battery is made up of highly flammable components^[4,5], such as the separator^[6-8] and the liquid electrolyte^[9], which consist of volatile carbonates such as dimethyl carbonate^[10] and ethyl methyl carbonate^[11]. In general, lithium-ion battery thermal runaway is the product of a chain of reactions that originate from a slight temperature rise caused by overcharge^[12,13], fast cycling, mechanical abuse^[14,15], or high ambient temperature^[16,17]. Under these circumstances, the cell temperature rises and causes the decomposition of the electrolyte^[18], releasing flammable gases which can be ignited in the presence of oxygen^[19].

Flame retardant additives incorporation into the electrolytes has been proposed as a promising solution to alleviate the catastrophic fires and explosions originating from the Li-ion batteries^[17,20-23]. However, despite the tremendous effort exerted towards achieving new safer electrolytes with electrochemical integrity, the safety diagnostics of the electrolytes have not advanced significantly. The common modalities in these diagnostic areas include direct burning tests using lighters^[24,25] and self-extinguishing time (SET) measurement^[26,27], which do not provide sufficient and reliable information about the fire behavior and hazard of liquid electrolytes. For instance, Wu et al.^[28] employed the critical oxygen index (COI), SET, and UL-94 tests to investigate the effect of the flame retardant additive on the fire behavior of an electrolyte containing ethoxy(pentafluoro)cyclotriphosphazene as a flame retardant. Although these tests provided some data regarding the fire behavior, they had limitations in providing critical parameters related to fire resistance, such as electrolyte ignition time and heat release behavior. In addition, the methods did not account for hazardous byproducts such as smoke and carbon monoxide produced by the electrolyte before and after flame retardant addition. Besides,

the UL-94 and SET methods employed for testing the electrolyte involve burning a fabric wetted using the electrolyte, limiting the reliability of the results obtained, as the fabric will also distort the heat release behavior of the electrolyte and toxic gases produced. Recently, Winter and co-workers developed a new device to characterize electrolyte flammability. They cited the non-reliability of the traditional SET measurements as their motivation due to the absence of data about the ignition source and the ignition time. The device is equipped with an ignition source, a sample holder, and a burning time recording software, allowing more measurements reproducibility [29]. Calorimetry methods such as the accelerating rate calorimetry (ARC)^[30,31], micro-calorimetry^[32], and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)^[33] have been used to study electrolyte fire behavior. Nevertheless, these calorimetric techniques are limited to only providing data about the thermal reactions of the electrolyte.

Cone calorimetry is a technique used to study the fire behavior of small samples of various materials in solid states^[34-36]. It is widely employed in fire safety engineering and is deemed the most effective bench scale technique in fire testing^[37]. The cone calorimeter gathers data regarding the ignition time, heat release rate, smoke, toxic gases, and other parameters associated with the specimen's burning properties.^[38] Its name comes from the conical shape of the radiant heater that produces a nearly uniform heat flux over the surface of the sample under study. The measurement of the heat release rate of materials using the cone calorimeter has become a routine part of fire testing for both research purposes and regulatory compliance. Hence, the heat release rate is a primary parameter in fire science which is foundational in modern fire protection engineering^[39]. However, the device has a limitation: its default sample holder is designed only to accommodate specimens in the solid-state such as solid polymers, woods, and other fabrics^[40,41]. The solid samples are directly laid onto a fiber backing pad made of asbestos^[42,43], which poses a fundamental issue for the stability and the accurate analysis of liquid samples, as the fiber would absorb some of the liquid specimens or cause a spill and leakage of the sample, before the initiation of the test. Therefore, the design of a new sample

holder that would enable the accurate and reliable measurement of liquid specimens' fire behavior and hazards is necessary.

Herein, we modified the cone calorimeter by introducing a custom-designed hollow cuboidal-shaped sample holder, enabling the fire resistance and hazards of liquid electrolytes to be diagnosed. This work is mainly intended to analyze the fire behavior and hazards of flame retardant-containing liquid electrolytes. This sample holder is designed to fit the sample stage and the heat flux coverage area of 100 cm^2 , with a pre-determined distance of 50 mm from the sample holder to the conical heater. This integration allows for fire behavior analysis of the electrolytes under a controlled temperature and heat flux. Besides, this current work also proposes that the new modified cone calorimetry method will be similarly effective in providing quantitative fire hazard diagnostic parameters such as smoke, CO, and CO₂ production. Therefore, this new method is expected to provide critical insight for scientists formulating safer electrolytes for lithium-ion batteries. Toward this, the performance of the sample holder prototype was first studied using dimethyl carbonate, and LiPF₆ in Ethylene carbonate (EC)/Ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC), from here referred to as LE. We verified its targeted function for enabling liquid electrolyte samples fire behavior to be diagnosed with high repeatability. The influence of sample volume on oxygen consumption is then assessed by testing different sample volumes to determine a cost-effective sample volume. Following promising results from these tests, the performance of the custom-designed accessory was further evaluated and demonstrated in diagnosing flame retardant-containing electrolyte samples. Accordingly, the fire resistance and hazard of LE containing different volume percent of flame retardant additive, ethoxy(pentafluoro)cyclotriphosphazene (from here referred to as FR) were investigated. Finally, the effect of heat flux on the critical fire behavior parameters of the flame retarded electrolyte such as time to ignition, peak heat release rate, total heat released and fire growth rate index, fire performance index, and smoke toxicity index was also investigated. The results from all these tests reveal the efficacy of the developed cuboidal-

shaped sample holder in lithium-ion battery electrolyte fire resistance and hazard diagnosis through the cone calorimetry technique.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Working Principle, Design, and Prototyping

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of cone calorimeter with the integrated sample holder.

The holding of the liquid-state samples on the sample stage, an essential requirement for the fire resistance and hazard diagnosis of the liquid electrolyte, is achieved using a custom-developed cuboidal shaped sample holder (**Figure 1b**, see **Figure S2b** for digital image). This sample holder was fabricated via 3D machining of stainless steel sheets. Stainless steel was selected due to its high corrosion resistance and thermal conductivity, which can easily enable the real-time measurement of the sample holder temperature evolution during fire testing. The sample holder has a cuboidal shape with the top side opened (**Figure 1e**), it has an inner area of 100cm^2 and a height of 2cm (**Figure 1f**), the sample holder can hold up to 150ml of electrolyte. However, a test sample of a volume of 10ml has been determined to provide reliable results. It

also has a handle that enables easy manipulation of the sample holder (Figure 1f). As illustrated in Figure 1c, the shape of the sample holder was designed to fit the shape of the sample stage and the heat flux area, which is situated under the smoke and gas transfer column of the cone calorimeter. The heat flux was measured by a Schmidt-Boelter-type heat flux meter. A controlled amount of heat flux can be applied to the electrolyte sample contained in the sample holder by adjusting the temperature of the conical heater (Figure 1b). This continuous heat supply to the electrolyte combined with an electric spark igniter (Figure 1b) in the presence of oxygen from the surrounding causes the sample to be ignited.

Figure 2. Profile of lithium-ion battery thermal runaway simulated based on the typical heat release profile obtained from the cone calorimeter.

Figure 2 represents a lithium-ion battery thermal runaway scenario using a typical heat release profile obtained from the cone calorimeter after a fire test. The time to ignition (TTI) (Figure 2, pink color), which is essentially the non-flammability threshold of the electrolyte, depends on the thermal inertia, critical heat flux, and critical surface temperature for ignition. After the electrolyte is ignited, the heat release rate curve rises (Figure 2 green colored arrow) until the fire is developed (Figure 2, dark blue colored arrow). After reaching the peak heat release rate, the combustion slows down, and eventually, the flame gets extinguished (Figure 2, purple colored arrow). The heat release rate is quantified by oxygen consumption calorimetry, which is based on Huggett's principle, i.e., the gross heat of combustion of any organic material is directly related to the amount of oxygen required for the material's combustion^[42].

The oxygen consumed during the electrolyte combustion is measured in real-time using a paramagnetic gas analyzer (Figure 1a) and recorded by a data acquisition unit. The heat release rate is computed automatically based on **Equation 1** by the Cone Cal Software connected to the cone calorimeter's gas analyzers.

$$\dot{q}'' = \frac{E(m^0O_2 - mO_2)}{A} \quad (1)^{[43]}$$

where \dot{q}'' is the heat release rate (kW/m^2), m^0O_2 and mO_2 are the mass flow rates of oxygen from the incoming air and in the exhaust duct, respectively (g s^{-1}), A is the initially exposed area of the sample (approximately taken as 0.01 m^2), $E = 13.1 \pm 5\% \text{ KJ g}^{-1}$ is the energy released per mass unit of O_2 consumed for a given fuel, as calculated by Huggett^[44].

Measurement of heat release from real fires by oxygen depletion calorimetry is well established based on Thornton's principle^[45]. It provides values that relate to the extent of burning. Furthermore, during combustion of the electrolyte, the effluent gases and smoke produced flows through the device's exhaust (Figure 1c) at a controlled flow rate. The effluent gases are then cooled to remove moisture and are analyzed using a paramagnetic oxygen analyzer and non-dispersive infrared CO and CO₂ analyzers. The quantity of smoke produced during the electrolyte combustion is measured using a laser smoke photometer (Figure 1d). The smoke produced is a crucial fire hazard parameter that can provide information about the possible toxicity that may result from electrolyte combustion.

Moreover, the total CO to CO₂ produced ratio provides the smoke toxicity index^[46]. The temperature of the conical heater, which heats the electrolyte, can be adjusted to match the battery cathode oxygen release temperature, hence mimicking the thermal runaway scenario more accurately. For this proof-of-concept study, we conducted the fire resistance and hazard diagnosis of the phosphazene (FR) containing LE at heat fluxes 10 kW m⁻² (450 °C) and 5 kW m⁻² (328 °C) which is close to the average temperature of oxygen release (300 °C) in lithium-ion battery cathodes as reported by Wang et. al^[23]. The exact test temperature and heat flux can be changed by programming the temperature controller.

2.2 Method Optimization Tests

Figure 3. Oxygen consumption profiles for different sample volumes of dimethyl carbonate a.) 5 ml b.) 10ml c.) 15 ml, and d.) 20 ml.

Preliminary optimization tests were carried out using the newly designed custom sample holder to probe the technique's repeatability and determine an optimal and cost-effective sample volume. For this purpose, dimethyl carbonate (DMC) was selected as a model solvent since it is a common constituent of the liquid electrolytes, and the obtained results were compared. Due to the low flash point of DMC (see Table S1 supporting information), the optimization tests were carried out by direct ignition (i.e., 0 kW m^{-2} heat flux) at room temperature without heating the sample by the conical heater. The oxygen consumption data of the DMC samples with different test sample volumes (5ml, 10ml, 15ml, and 20 ml) are presented in **Figure 3 and 4**. Each of the tests was repeated three times to establish the repeatability of the technique. The data obtained from all three samples exhibited a similar and nearly identical trend. When the

peak oxygen consumed value of the respective tests were compared, it was found that the data of all the samples was reproducible with a minimal standard deviation range between 0.057 – 0.46%, which is in accordance with the 10% widely accepted error tolerance range of the cone calorimetry results^[47]. To determine a cost-effective specimen volume for the test method, experiments were conducted using different sample volumes of DMC, and the results were compared. Accordingly, the 5 ml DMC samples exhibited a decreased peak oxygen consumption compared to the 10 ml, 15 ml, and 20 ml DMC samples (Figure 3b, 3c, and 3d). It was observed that the peak oxygen consumption remained relatively similar regardless of the sample volume; this phenomenon is attributed to the nature of the fuel, i.e., liquid state. In contrast, the total oxygen consumed (a time integration of the oxygen consumption curve) showed a linear trend with increased sample volume from 5 ml to 20 ml (Figure 4a, 4b, 4c, and 4d), which can be attributed to the sustained combustion due to the larger amount fuel.

Figure 4. Total oxygen consumed profiles for different sample volumes of dimethyl carbonate a.) 5 ml b.) 10ml c.) 15 ml, and d.) 20 ml.

Figure 5a illustrates the trend of the peak oxygen consumption with a change in volume of DMC. From **Figure 5b and 5c**, it can be seen that the total oxygen consumed and the burning time show a strong dependence on the sample volume. In contrast, the peak oxygen consumed values (Figure 5a) remained quite similar for samples with a volume of 10 ml, 15 ml, and 20 ml. As the peak heat release rate (the most important parameter during fire behavior analysis) is directly proportional to the peak oxygen consumed, therefore it could be concluded that the 10ml sample volume is sufficient to obtain data regarding the fire behavior of electrolytes.

Figure 5. a) Peak oxygen consumed, b.) Total oxygen consumed at 100s c.) Burning time distribution for different sample volumes of dimethyl carbonate.

Furthermore, it was observed that the mean peak oxygen consumed value of the sample with 10ml specimen volume was equal to the mean value of all the test samples: 0.142 g/s and while was exhibiting a low standard deviation of 0.46% (**Table S5**). Therefore, the 10 ml specimen volume was chosen as the optimum specimen volume for the flame retardant containing electrolytes. This specimen volume provides clear and sufficient fire behavior data to characterize fire resistance and hazard of flame retarded liquid electrolytes using the cone calorimeter. Thus, opening a new avenue to design safer battery electrolytes. The above results suggest that the designed accessory enabled the cone calorimeter to determine the fire resistance

and hazards of flame retarded liquid electrolyte samples. It provided accurate fire behavior data, with a negligible error percentage, for each sample volume that was tested.

Moreover, as seen in Equation 1, the cone calorimeter data such as peak heat release rate (pHRR) and total heat released (THR) are normalized based on the exposed area of the sample. The exposed area is approximately 100 mm x 100 mm equivalent to a surface area of 0.01 m². In this study, rather than spatial normalization, a volumetric approach is proposed and followed due to the state of the sample being liquid, not solid. Therefore, we proposed **Equation 2** for liquid heat release rate calculation, where exposed sample area, A from Equation 1 is substituted by exposed sample volume, V.

$$\dot{q}''_{liq} = \frac{E (m^0O_2 - mO_2)}{V} \quad (2)$$

where \dot{q}''_{liq} is the heat release rate (kW L⁻¹) for liquid samples, m^0O_2 and mO_2 are the mass flow rates of oxygen from the incoming air and in the exhaust duct, respectively (g s⁻¹), V is the exposed volume of the sample (L or dm³), $E = 13.1 \pm 5\%$ KJ g⁻¹ is the energy released per mass unit of O₂ consumed for a given fuel, as calculated by Huggett.

As the determined optimal sample volume is 10ml is equivalent to 0.01 L. For convenience, it is proposed that the denominator unit of the output data obtained from the cone calorimeter is corrected from m² to L or dm³ for liquid sample tests such as electrolytes. This correction is due to the 1:1 equivalence of the determined optimal liquid specimen volume with the standard area of solid samples (0.01 m²). (see Equation S1, S2 in supporting information for the detailed calculation). Consequently, the units of THR, fire growth rate index (FIGRA) and fire performance index (FPI) were also modified accordingly.

2.3 Fire behavior of Standard Carbonate Liquid Electrolyte

Figure 6. a.) Heat release profile b.) Total heat released profile c.) Fire growth rate index and d.) carbon monoxide production profile for 1M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC, measured at a heat flux of 0 kW m⁻² (all data measured are presented in triplicates).

Following the encouraging results with DMC, we tested the integrated sample holder for real-time fire behavior analysis of a standard carbonate liquid electrolyte sample, 1M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC (LE). Similarly, this experiment was carried out at a heat flux of 0 kW m⁻², i.e., without supplying any heat from the conical heater. 10 ml of the samples were transferred into the designed sample holder covered by an aluminum foil and then placed on the sample stage. The ignition was provided by an external lighter. The sample was ignited instantly, and the gas analysis system continuously measured the oxygen consumption data.

Moreover, the data acquisition unit transferred the data to the software to compute the critical fire hazard parameters such as peak heat release rate (pHRR), total heat released (THR), and carbon monoxide produced (COP). The smoke laser photometer measured the total smoke

produced (TSP), which is crucial because the smoke causes so much damage to human beings during fire accidents. According to **Figure 6**, it can be observed that all the test parameters measured and computed, such as pHRR, THR, COP, and fire growth rate index (FIGRA), fire performance index (FPI), are accurate with high reproducibility.

2.4 Fire Resistance Diagnosis of flame retardant containing Liquid Electrolyte

Figure 7. Qualitative GC-MS chromatograms of the standard liquid electrolyte (LE) (black), FR (red), 2vol% FR in LE (blue), 4vol% FR in LE, and 6vol% FR in LE b). Mass spectra of standard liquid electrolyte (LE) and FR.

To confirm the presence of FR in LE, a qualitative analysis was performed using gas chromatography coupled to a mass spectrometer (GC-MS). **Figure 7** shows the gas chromatography retention times and mass spectra of LE, FR, and LE with various content of FR. Based on the mass spectra (Figure 7b), the retention time at 7.68 min corresponds to LE while at 3.61 min corresponds to the FR. Hence, as seen in Figure 7a, all the flame retarded electrolyte samples exhibited two characteristic peaks at 7.68 min and 3.61 min, confirming their composition.

Figure 8. a.) Heat release profile b.) Total heat released profile for LE containing various content of flame retardant additive (FR) measured at a heat flux of 10 kW m^{-2} c.) Heat release profile d.) Total heat released profile for LE containing various content of flame retardant additive (FR), measured at a heat flux of 5 kW m^{-2} .

Moreover, the integrated sample holder was tested for real-time fire resistance diagnosis of liquid electrolyte samples containing a phosphazene-based flame retardant. This experiment employed different volume percent (2, 4, and 6 volume %) of ethoxy pentafluorophosphazene as a flame retardant additive in the liquid electrolyte. 10 ml of the flame retardant containing samples were poured into the designed sample holder covered by an aluminum foil. Then, the sample stage was placed under the conical heater. The tests were carried out at different heat fluxes (0 , 5 , and 10 kW m^{-2}) corresponding to different test temperatures (all the tests were carried out in duplicates with high result reproducibility, see Table S6 and S7).

Similarly, the gas analysis system measured the oxygen consumption data while the data acquisition unit transferred the data to the software to compute the critical fire hazard parameters. Notably, at a heat flux of 0 kW m^{-2} , all the flame retarded electrolyte samples could not be ignited, and therefore no data was obtained from the cone calorimeter. **Figure 8a, 8b, 8c, and 8d** illustrate real-time heat release data of the phosphazene-based flame retarded liquid electrolytes obtained based on the oxygen consumption of the samples during combustion at a heat flux of 5 and 10 kW m^{-2} . This data was obtained directly from the Cone Cal 5 software, which shows key fire resistance characteristics of the specimen, such as time to ignition (TTI) of the flame retarded electrolyte, which gives insight about rescue possibility during a battery thermal runaway or fire incident. It was found that the addition of FR to the electrolyte had a significant effect to further delay the time to ignition (TTI) of the electrolyte, which increases to 65 seconds for the LE-6FR compared to 5 seconds for the pristine LE at a heat flux of 10 kW m^{-2} (Figure 8a).

Furthermore, as illustrated in Figure 8b, compared to the total heat released by the pristine electrolyte (LE), the FR-containing electrolytes showed a decreased amount of total heat released during combustion. However, no significant impact of the FR was observed on the peak heat release rate due to the gas-phase mechanism of this flame retardant. Besides, the toxic gas production and smoke toxicity index (ratio of total CO produced to total CO_2 produced) data are provided in **Table S2 and S3**. Interestingly, with the increased quantity of FR in the electrolyte, the smoke toxicity index at a heat flux of 10 kW m^{-2} increased from 0.01033 to 0.0193 for LE and LE-6FR, respectively. Meanwhile, the total carbon monoxide produced at the same heat flux was also found to increase with increased FR content from 0.18 g to 0.24 g for samples LE and LE-6FR, respectively.

In addition, at 5 kW m^{-2} heat flux which corresponds to a $328 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ test temperature, the flame retarded electrolytes exhibited a similar trend in heat release behavior, with a more than 50%

decrease in the total heat released from 15.9 MJ L⁻¹ to 7.88 MJ L⁻¹ for the pristine electrolyte (LE) and LE-6FR respectively. Similarly, no significant change was observed in the pHRR due to the gas phase action of the flame retardant. Notably, more than 2 minutes of ignition delay was observed for the LE-6FR sample compared to the pristine electrolyte (LE). Essentially, the TTI increased from 10s to 145s for LE and LE-6FR, respectively. In addition, the smoke and toxic gas production data are also provided in **Figure S1** and **S2**. Similarly, with the increased quantity of FR in the electrolyte, the total smoke produced (TSP) at a heat flux of 5 kW m⁻² increased from 0.127 m² to 0.153 m² for samples LE-2FR and LE-4FR, respectively. While the total carbon monoxide produced at the same heat flux was increased from 0.193 g to 0.206 g for samples LE-2FR and LE-4FR, respectively. **Table 1** summarizes the critical fire behavior parameters obtained from the cone calorimetry test for the pristine electrolyte (LE) and flame retarded electrolytes.

Table 1. Parameters of LE with content flame retardant additive (FR) obtained from cone calorimeter at different heat fluxes.

Sample	Heat Flux	TTI^a	pHRR^b	THR^c	FIGRA^d	FPI^e
	kW. m⁻²	s	kW. L⁻¹	MJ L⁻¹	kW. L⁻¹.s⁻¹	s. L/kW
LE	5	10	259	18.2	7.40	0.039
LE	10	5	252	20.1	7.20	0.020
LE-2FR	5	45	242	10.6	3.23	0.186
LE-2FR	10	10	241	19.6	5.35	0.041
LE-4FR	5	115	251	9.29	1.86	0.458
LE-4FR	10	20	260	18.8	4.73	0.077
LE-6FR	5	145	243	7.88	1.47	0.597
LE-6FR	10	65	254	14.5	2.99	0.256

a) TTI: time to ignition; b) pHRR: peak heat release rate; c) THR: total heat released; d) FIGRA: fire growth rate index; e) FPI: fire performance index.

Furthermore, in addition to the parameters discussed above, Table 1 also presents the fire growth rate index (FIGRA) of the flame retarded electrolyte samples; it is the ratio of pHRR to time to pHRR^[48]. Essentially, it was found that the FIGRA reduced with the increased loading of FR at both heat fluxes of 5 and 10 kW m⁻². Moreover, the fire performance index(FPI); (the ratio of TTI to pHRR) was also computed. The FPI indicates the safety rank of materials; the higher FPI value shows the higher safety rank of the material^[49]. Consequently, at a heat flux of 5 kW m⁻², the LE-6FR sample exhibited a high FPI value of 0.597 compared to 0.039 for LE. The FIGRA and FPI results show that introducing FR into the electrolyte can act effectively to reduce the fire propagation rate and flashover risk, hence decreasing the extent of damage during battery thermal runaway or fire accidents.

3. Conclusion

In summary, a reliable fire-resistance and hazard diagnostic technique has been demonstrated for flame retarded liquid electrolytes using a custom-designed cuboidal sample holder integrated into the cone calorimeter. The newly designed sample holder was incorporated into the cone calorimeter to analyze the fire hazards and behavior of flame retarded liquid electrolytes. The preliminary optimizations tests carried out using DMC showed that a 10ml cost-effective test sample volume was sufficient to obtain similar fire behavior data results with higher sample volume. The accessory was employed to diagnose the fire resistance of a phosphazene flame retardant containing electrolyte and real-time fire resistance and hazard parameters such as heat release rate, time to ignition, and smoke produced were successfully measured. All the acquired data were shown to be reliable with negligibly minor variations. These results suggest that the developed technique could be a good candidate for diagnosing the fire resistance and hazards of flame retarded liquid electrolytes. The method potentially offers more comprehensive fire safety diagnostic applications for other metal-ion battery flame retarded liquid electrolytes.

4. Experimental

Design and Fabrication of the sample holder: The 3D sample holder was constructed by a precision machining of 304 stainless steel sheets with a thickness of 4 mm. The stainless steel sheets were coupled into a cuboidal shape by welding the five parts together. Furthermore, a handle was also welded to the sample holder to allow easy manipulation. Subsequently, all the coupled parts of the sample holder were smoothed using an abrasive.

Sample holder integration: The sample holder was coupled to the cone calorimeter by placing it directly on the sample stage. The fire resistance and hazard diagnosis of the flame retardant liquid electrolyte was conducted by placing the electrolyte samples into the custom-designed sample holder covered by aluminum foil to prevent the risk of corrosion.

Flame retarded electrolyte preparation: The flame retarded electrolyte was prepared by the addition of different volume percent (2, 4, and 6%) of ethoxy(pentafluoro)cyclotriphosphazene into the 1M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC (1:1 v/v) electrolyte. The final sample volume for each composition was 10 ml.

Fire resistance and hazard diagnosis: The fire behavior of all the samples was investigated using a cone calorimeter (FTT, UK). 10 ml of the electrolyte specimen was transferred into the sample holder. Then the sample holder containing the electrolyte was then laid onto the cone calorimeter's sample stage. The thermal aggression was provided by an external heat flux using the radiant conical heater of the device. This sample holder and heater do not introduce any additional fuel source to trigger the ignition of the electrolyte as that would otherwise interfere with emissions of effluent gases from the sample under testing. After combustion, fire products are captured. The in-situ online analysis of the fire products includes the quantification of

consumed O₂ (using the paramagnetic analyzer), CO, and CO₂ using non-dispersive infrared analyzers the smoke produced was measured using a laser photometer.

Qualitative analysis of electrolyte and flame retardant: The liquid electrolytes with different content of FR were analyzed using the gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. The analysis was carried out using a Trace GC Ultra Gas Chromatograph (Thermo Scientific) coupled to a low-resolution Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (model DSQ II, Thermo Scientific) and Auto-sampler for liquid injection (Triplus AS). The column used was a Phenomenex ZB-5 (30 m * 0.25 mm * 0.25 μm). Samples were diluted in the ratio of 20:980 with acetonitrile. Further method was adopted from Grützke et al.^[50]. At an injection temperature of 200 °C, 1 μl of the diluted sample was injected. Helium was used as carrier gas with a flow of 1.2 mL/min and a split of 50. The transfer line temperature was set at 230 °C while the oven temperature ramp used was: 40 °C for 3 minutes, then at 12 °C/min up to 85 °C and 30 °C/min up to 200 °C and held for 1 minute. The measurements were carried out with an ion source temperature of 230 °C, the solvent delay was 3 minutes, and the masses were recorded in positive mode between m/z 30 and 800. ¹H NMR, ¹³C, and ³¹P NMR spectra of LE-FR samples were acquired using a Bruker spectrometer. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis of the LE-FR samples was performed on a Thermofisher Nicolet 5700 spectrometer in ATR mode.

Data Analysis: All cone calorimetry tests were carried out in triplicates. The fire behavior and hazard data were directly obtained from the Cone Cal 5 Software. The statistical data presented, such as mean and standard deviation, were analyzed using Origin Graphing & Analysis program (2019 Version).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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